

THE NECESSITY OF USING SINGAPORE TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The implementation of Singaporean educational technology in Uzbekistan is considered a promising direction. The Singapore education system is recognized worldwide as one of the most effective systems, based on a constructivist approach. This article discusses the scientific foundations of using Singaporean pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of preschool education. In particular, the main principles, advantages, and the necessity of practical implementation of Singapore methodology are analyzed.

Keywords: preschool education, quality of education, Singapore technology, CPA model, logical thinking, problem-solving and creative skills, quality education, innovative approach, constructivist approach.

The quality of preschool education is determined by the level of children's comprehensive development. In this process, the formation of cognitive, social, and emotional skills is especially important. High-quality education provided at this stage creates a strong foundation for success in subsequent stages of education. According to modern pedagogical views, preschool education should not be limited to providing knowledge only, but should also develop life skills such as independent thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making.

In today's globalized world, improving the quality of education requires the use of innovative and effective pedagogical technologies. In this regard, the

Singapore methodology helps children achieve deep understanding, independent thinking, and creative approaches. Improving quality in preschool education is one of the most important tasks today, requiring special attention to the development of children's logical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity.

Therefore, the use of Singapore technology in improving preschool education quality has significant scientific and practical importance. In particular, the learning process organized based on the CPA (Concrete–Pictorial–Abstract) model is an effective tool for developing children's thinking. Through this model, children gradually acquire knowledge and enhance their logical thinking and cognitive activity. Thus, adapting and implementing this advanced experience into the national education system is an urgent task. According to this approach, children do not receive knowledge in a ready-made form but construct it independently through active learning. The Singapore methodology, developed in the 1980s, focuses on deep understanding, problem-solving, and conceptual learning. It is widely recognized as one of the most effective education systems in the world and is based on a constructivist approach. The Singapore methodology teaches children to seek answers to the questions “why?” and “how?”. This develops logical thinking and problem-solving skills from an early age, contributing to future academic and life success. The technology teaches through games and problem situations. Children solve tasks through practical activities and play, making learning engaging and memorable. Singapore preschool education technologies, unlike traditional memorization-based approaches, are based on:

In the Singapore preschool education system, several modern pedagogical technologies and approaches are used. Their main goal is to develop children's independent thinking, logical reasoning, and problem-solving skills. In Singapore methodology, the following tools are widely used:

Therefore, these technologies are considered one of the most effective ways to ensure quality education today.

Main Principles of the Singapore Methodology

Singapore technology can be applied in preschool education through the following methods:

- Didactic games: “Count and find”, “Match correctly”, “Find the extra item”;
- Problem situations: encouraging children to solve tasks independently;
- Visual materials: cards, colored blocks, diagrams;
- Group work: developing communication and idea exchange skills.

Singapore technology is a pedagogical approach that organizes the learning process based on active learning, deep understanding, and logical thinking. It is recognized globally as one of the most effective educational systems, especially in mathematics. The methodology teaches children not to memorize knowledge, but to

understand and apply it. It is particularly effective in developing logical thinking and problem-solving skills in preschool-aged children.

CPA Model (Core of Singapore Technology)

		Showing 3 apples in a picture
	Reinforcing knowledge using numbers and symbols	

This approach helps children deeply understand concepts and develop logical thinking.

Pedagogical Benefits of Singapore Technology

- Development of logical and critical thinking;
- Deep understanding of knowledge rather than superficial learning;
- Formation of problem-solving skills;
- Making the learning process engaging and interactive;
- Development of independent thinking and creativity.

Unlike traditional memorization-based approaches, this methodology emphasizes finding answers to the question “why?”.

In the context of globalization, the need to modernize the education system is increasing. In this regard, implementing Singapore experience in preschool education is important for the following reasons:

The Singapore experience shows that the quality of education depends not only on the curriculum but also on the methodology of its implementation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, introducing Singapore technology in preschool education institutions in Uzbekistan is an effective and necessary way to improve education quality. Through the CPA model and interactive methods, children's knowledge and skills are deeply developed, and their logical thinking, creativity, and independent decision-making abilities are enhanced. Therefore, the implementation of this methodology in the national preschool education system is an actual task.

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